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The transcriptional landscape of luminal B subtype breast cancer in humans: CDCA3.

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Breast cancer in humans is a solid tumor type with distinct subtypes historically defined by the PAM50 molecular subtype classification scheme (1-3). We utilize, in this study, whole transcriptome technologies to define the transcriptional landscape of luminal B subtype human breast cancer (4, 5). We describe here differential expression of CDCA3 in luminal B breast cancer.

1 We harnessed the power of whole transcriptome technology, using only primary tumor tissues from
2 patients with breast cancer of defined molecular subtype (4, 5) to perform differential gene expression
3 analyses, for characterization, in molecular detail, of the tumor transcriptome of luminal B subtype breast
4 cancer.

5 **Methods**

6 We utilized microarray datasets GSE45827 (4) and GSE87049 (5) for this global differential gene
7 expression analysis of luminal B subtype human breast cancer in conjunction with the R-based
8 computational differential gene expression software GEO2R. GSE45827 was generated using
9 [HG-U133_Plus_2] Affymetrix Human Genome U133 Plus 2.0 Array technology with $n=11$ normal breast
10 tissues (control) and $n=30$ luminal B subtype primary tumors from humans with breast cancer; analysis
11 was performed using GPL570. GSE87049 was generated using Affymetrix Human Gene 1.0 ST Array
12 [transcript (gene) version] technology with $n=35$ normal breast tissues (control) $n=27$ primary breast
13 tumors of luminal B subtype from humans with breast cancer; analysis was performed using platform
14 GPL6244. We used an R-based bioinformatic tool to perform whole transcriptome co-regulation studies
15 across multiple tissues (SEEK [6]). We utilized a computational tool to measure the influence of tumor
16 gene expression on overall survival in humans with breast cancer, in $n=1879$ patients (total), in $n=431$
17 basal subtype patients, in $n=596$ luminal A subtype patients, in $n=439$ luminal B subtype patients, in
18 $n=362$ HER2+ patients, and $n=51$ normal-like subtype patients (7).

14 **Rationale**

15 Breast cancer in humans is a complex molecular entity that remains to be completely defined.

17 **Results**

18 We performed whole transcriptome profiling - subtraction analysis, also known as differential gene
19 expression profiling - to identify and describe at the systems level the complete set of genes whose
20 expression was most specifically activated or repressed in humans with the luminal B subtype of human
21 breast cancer.

21 1. Primary tumors of the breast from humans with breast cancer: luminal B subtype

22 $n=11$ normal breast tissues (human)

23 $n=30$ primary tumors (breast; human; luminal B)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
223307_at	4.30E-11	-8.8258305	15.03012	-2.6564103	CDCA3	1410/29873	95.3

24
25
26 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal breast tissues and luminal B breast
27 tumors, we discovered differential expression of cell division cycle associated 3, encoded by CDCA3
28 (located at 12p13) in luminal B breast cancer in humans (Chart 1). The expression of CDCA3 changed
more than 95% of the human breast and breast tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose
expression was measured - in this case, 29,873 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the negative fold-change

1 indicating increased quantity of CDCA3 messenger RNA in luminal B subtype tumors, demonstrating
 2 up-regulation of CDCA3 during transformation of the breast from normal breast tissue to luminal B breast
 3 cancer.

4 2. Primary tumors of the breast from humans with breast cancer: luminal B subtype

5 $n=35$ normal breast tissues (human)

6 $n=27$ primary tumors (breast; human; luminal B)

7 ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
7960702	5.58E-18	-12.0177895	30.603655	-1.1966994	CDCA3	106/33297	99.7

8
 9 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal breast tissues and luminal B breast
 10 tumors in a second microarray dataset from independent investigators and a separate patient cohort, we
 11 validated differential expression of CDCA3 in luminal B breast cancer in humans (Chart 2). The
 12 expression of CDCA3 here changed more than 99% of the human breast and breast tumor transcriptome
 13 when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 33,297 transcripts
 (“Rank”). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of CDCA3 messenger RNA in
 luminal B subtype tumors, demonstrating up-regulation of CDCA3 during transformation of the breast
 from normal breast tissue to luminal B breast cancer.

14 Thus, CDCA3 is a gene whose differential expression defines the transcriptional landscape of the
 15 luminal B breast cancer subtype in humans.

16 In breast cancer as in any solid tumor, the function of the gene identified by whole transcriptome
 17 differential gene expression cannot be assumed to be the same as in non-transformed tissues. Thus, to
 18 identify gene products likely to interact with and/or be relevant to the differentially expressed genes
 19 function in the transformed tissue, we performed whole transcriptome transcriptional co-regulation studies
 20 using SEEK, an R-based computational tool that blindly and quantitatively identifies co-expression across
 21 the genome using a clustering method rather than integration-based differential gene expression
 methodology (6). This second whole transcriptome technology identified CDC20, KIF2C, UBE2C,
 AURKB, and FOXM1 as the five genes across the transcriptome most closely co-regulated with CDCA3
 in the transformed human breast (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1: Transcriptional co-regulation in the transformed human breast: CDCA3.

Finally, we evaluated the influence of CDCA3 tumor gene expression on overall survival (**Figure 2**) (7).

Fig. 2: Relationship between CDCA3 tumor expression and overall survival in humans with breast cancer.

Caption: Overall survival in all patients (above; left), in patients with basal subtype (above; center), in patients with luminal A subtype (above; right), in patients with luminal B subtype (below; left), in patients with HER2+ subtype (below; center), and patients with normal-like subtype breast cancer (below; right) is depicted in these Kaplan-Meier plots.

Discussion

We describe here CDCA3 as a component gene product of the luminal B subtype in human breast cancer, suggesting its importance in the development or maintenance of the subtype, a product of tumor evolution in transformation of solid tissues in humans.

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